

**MAIN CONTENT CHARACTERISTICS OF GENERAL SCIENCES
COMPETENCES OF THE FUTURE IT TEACHER.**

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Abstract. Third-generation standards are introduced in the higher education systems of our republic. One of her main focuses is the competency-based approach to teaching. This article describes the essential features of the future computer science teacher's specific competencies in information technology.

Keywords: Competence, information technology, user competence, programming competence, multimedia competence, network technology competence.

Third-generation standards are introduced in the higher education systems of our republic. One of her main focuses is the competency-based approach to teaching. This also applies to the training of future teachers, including computer science teachers. The concept of "competence" is not new in pedagogy. The scientific work of scientists has implemented this definition in teacher training: as a method of implementing the system of professional knowledge and skills; personal characteristics of the teacher; as an indicator of teacher education; as a certain value. In other words, competence is considered by the authors from various scientific approaches: personality, activity, knowledge, system-structural, psychological, cultural, etc. Under competence, we consider the ability to use knowledge, skills and personal qualities to be successful in a certain field.

We consider the modern interpretation of the concept of information technology. First, we emphasize the main differences between the concepts of

"technology" and "tools". Technology is a set of production methods and processes in a certain field of production, and techniques used in any business. Tools are means (objects, devices, or a combination thereof) necessary to perform any activity. Let's consider the concepts of "information technology" and "information technology tools". One of the main concepts of the scientific field of "informatics" is the concept of "information technologies".

Information technology is a set of automated collection, processing, storage, transmission, use, production means and methods of data to obtain known, clearly expected results [1,2]

Therefore, the use of information technologies in education allows the collection, storage, processing, output and reproduction of all types of information. Information technology includes the main technological processes, basic and specialized information technologies, and tool base. We emphasize the main possibilities of information technologies:

- implementation of modern software, software-hardware and technical tools and devices working on the basis of microprocessor and computer technologies, the transmission of information resources, means of transmission and systems, information exchange;

- use of special formalisms (logical-linguistic models) to express declarative and procedural knowledge in electronic form;

- providing an interactive mode of communication between the user and the system using professional programming languages and artificial intelligence tools;

- ensuring the interaction of information between the user and the computer, eliminating the need for regulatory assistance.

Information technology tools (IT tools) are software, hardware and software, and hardware and devices that work on the basis of microprocessor computing technology [2]. These include information transmission, information exchange tools and systems that provide opportunities for data collection, production, storage,

processing, transmission and use of information resources in local and global computer networks. Information technology tools include:

- - computers;
- -local computer networks, all kinds of modern means of communication, provide information interaction of users both locally and globally; all types of information input-output devices;
- - means and devices for manipulating text, graphics, and audiovisual information and broadcasting it;
- - means of archiving data of any size;
- - devices for digital and reverse image conversion;
- - computer graphic systems; software systems and complexes (programming languages, translators, compilers, operating systems, tool packages for the development of application software, including those implemented in networks, application software packages, etc.);

artificial intelligence systems; electronic tools for educational purposes based on multimedia technologies, hypertext, hypermedia and telecommunications.

Note that a synonym of the term "information technology" can be the term "information-communication technology", which emphasizes the inclusion of the concept of communication technology in the framework that provides the transmission of meaning through a communication channel. Communication technologies are designed to provide quick communication and access to information resources in any field of knowledge without limiting the size and speed, to ensure information interaction of users at the local or global level. Informatization tools for educational purposes are called information technology tools that are used together with educational, methodological, normative, technical and organizational-instructional materials that ensure the implementation of the optimal technology of their pedagogical use.

The pedagogical effectiveness of using such tools as electronic tools for educational purposes, software and hardware complexes for studying a certain subject, and automated educational systems largely depends on the level of development of educational and methodological documents. The lack of detailed methodological recommendations on the use of electronic tools (electronic textbooks, Internet educational resources, etc.) for educational purposes limits the use of these software products in pedagogical practice [3].

The following didactic problems solved with the help of information technologies can be distinguished:

- improvement of teaching organization, increase of individualization of education;
- increase the efficiency of students' self-training;
- individualization of the teacher's work;
- acceleration of access to achievements of pedagogical practice;
- increase motivation for learning;
- the possibility of activating the educational process, involving students in research activities;
- ensuring the flexibility of the educational process.

So we can conclude:

- modern information technology tools play an important role in the educational process;
- it is necessary to form a system of knowledge, skills and qualifications of future teachers on the use of information technologies in the teaching and learning process.

The analysis of the information available in the literature on the use of modern advances in computer technology in higher education showed that in order to successfully solve the problems facing the future computer science teacher, he needs the following knowledge and skills:

- use of global and scientific-educational computer networks;
- creating software tools for use in the educational process together with students based on modern programming achievements (hypertext and multimedia technologies);
- organization of individual, group and collective activities of students using IT tools in educational and extracurricular activities;
- use of computer placement systems for various purposes: publication of wall newspapers, design of educational materials, etc. [4, 5].

Based on the tasks faced by the computer science teacher in professional activity, we distinguish the following subject competencies in the field of IT: user competence, programming competence, competence in the field of multimedia, competence in the field of network technologies.

Let's define each of these competencies.

User competence. As mentioned above, the teacher of computer science has a special role, because this subject is always moving forward. Today, a computer science teacher must not only teach his students the basics of computer science, but also perform the functions of adapting the content of computer science education to the ever-changing hardware and software. A computer science teacher should be able to work in several operating systems, work with various types of data (text, graphics, video, audio, etc.), for this he should know practical programs for several operating systems, as well as word processing systems, digital tables, must work with graphics, databases, integrated environments, the Internet, and more.

Therefore, by user competence we understand the set of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for working with information, presenting it in a form convenient for computer processing in any operating system, working with hardware and software, as well as managing personal computers.

To form user competencies, it should solve the following educational tasks:

- learning to work with operating systems;

- learning to work with computer programs;
- learning to work with information and communication, computer technologies, including text processing systems, digital tables, graphics, databases, integrated environments, the Internet, etc.

Competence in programming. Programming is one of the main components of computer science, so we should give it due attention. A computer science teacher must have programming skills in several procedural and object-oriented languages, have tested skills, have the basics of web programming, create software training products, and have computer modeling methodologies and their subsequent implementation.

Therefore, under the competence of the future computer science teacher in the field of programming, we consider that the computer science teacher has the knowledge, skills and abilities to solve educational problems in a particular programming language, to choose the appropriate approach to algorithm development depending on the specifics of the problem being solved, as well as to create a ready-made software educational product. We understand the ability to apply personal qualities.

To form competence in the field of programming, it is necessary to solve the following educational tasks:

- teaching algorithm basics;
- learning procedural programming;
- learning object-oriented programming;
- learning web programming;
- Learning to create educational software products (professional programming).

Multimedia competence. Multimedia (multi-many, media-environment, that is, many environments) is "the simultaneous use of various forms of information presentation and processing in one container object." In other words, multimedia is

a modern computer information technology that allows combining various types of information such as text, graphics, photos, animation, video, sound in a single information environment. Currently, this is one of the most promising and popular areas of computer science, its goal is to create a product that includes images, texts and data synthesis, audio, video, animation and interactive control mechanisms, along with other audio and visual effects.

With the competence of a future computer science teacher in the field of multimedia, we understand the ability of the computer science teacher to use knowledge, skills and personal qualities to work with tests, graphics, audio, data sets, video data, animation, as well as create multimedia products.

To form competence in the field of multimedia, it is necessary to solve the following educational tasks:

- teaching the basics of computer graphics;
- teaching the basics of working with audio materials;
- teaching the basics of working with video materials;
- learning the basics of working with animation;
- teaching how to create multimedia educational products.

Competence in the field of network technologies. Currently, network technologies and WWW have firmly entered the life of society. The existence of WWW has changed the nature of the educational process. Modern networking technologies improve everyone's ability to communicate and give people around the world unprecedented access to information. Today, they have become a necessary foundation of computer science, so today it is impossible to imagine an informatics curriculum that does not pay much attention to this topic, not only in the training of future informatics teachers but also in other areas, network technologies have become an important pedagogical tool. Therefore, in our opinion, the formation of competencies of the future computer science teacher in the field of network technologies is a necessary condition for his professionalism.

In educational institutions, these functions (software and technical support of the information-educational environment) are entrusted to the teacher of computer science, who must have training in this area, and have a level of competence in network technologies.

Thus, within the framework of competence in network technologies, we consider the ability of a computer science teacher to use knowledge, skills and personal qualities to implement effective activities in educational design, creation, change, provision and management of computer networks, as well as the ability to manage user information network resources in the teaching of computer science. We understand that.

To form network competence, it should solve the following educational tasks:

- teaching the basics of network technologies and educational computer environment, including design, configuration, maintenance and management of hardware, software and information components;
- mastering network technologies to manage the development of the information-educational environment within the educational institution;
- mastering network technologies to manage the process of using information network resources in the teaching of computer science

The formation of this competence allows future teachers of informatics to create and develop an informational, educational environment of an educational institution based on modern information technologies, as well as to organize an educational process using network technologies.

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